

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 11

JANUARY-MARCH ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. CHRISTINE JOY A. REFUELO

Assistant Professor III

Apayao State College

cjanzado19@gmail.com

“THE HEARTBEAT OF THE COMMUNITY”

In every community, where young minds grow,
A teacher's light shines and glow.
Beyond the four-walled room,
Their guide, love, and hope bloom.

They plant the seeds of wisdom and care,
Encouraging dreams no one can compare.
With patient hands and determined voice,
They help every learner find a choice.

In the community they stand so strong.
You can feel their presence-they belong.
Fighting for right and correcting wrong,
Through lessons taught and influence along.

They work with parents, hand in hand,
Lifting each child to understand
That learning's path is bright,
Even to students with dim light.

Through service, guidance they start
Not only teaching books and art.
Building minds and shaping heart,
Teachers make us smart.

A teacher's role is more than seen;
They shape what tomorrow will mean.
Within the school and community too,
Their mission is to guide us through.

